

Design, construction and operation of a particle-driven CSP conveyance loop: attrition, erosion, and thermal performance aspects

Yimin Deng^{a,b}, Alex Le Gal^c, Emmanuel Guillot^c, Gilles Flamant^{c,*}, Jan Baeyens^{b,*}

^a Beijing Institute of Technology, School of Chemistry and Chemical Engineering, 102248 Beijing, China

^b European Powder & Process Technology (EPPT), 9 Park Tremeland, 3120 Tremelo, Belgium

^c PROMES-CNRS (UPR 8521), 7 Rue du Four Solaire, 66120 Font-Romeu Odeillo, France

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ABSTRACT

This study presents a novel particle-driven Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) system, focusing on the design and operation of its dense-phase particle conveyance loop. Contrary to well-documented lean-phase conveying, the dense-phase mode significantly reduces heat losses and particle velocity, thereby mitigating attrition and erosion. Through experimental analysis and engineering modeling, we demonstrate the feasibility of vertically conveying 16 t/h of olivine particles within a 0.20 m diameter riser over 90 m height, achieving a specific energy consumption of 0.35 kW/ton-53% lower than conventional bucket elevators. Key findings include a remarkably low particle attrition rate (<0.1% per cycle) and an extrapolated component lifespan of 16-24 years for selected materials (AISI 410/304 for risers/screw conveyors at ~ 300 °C and AISI 310 for the down-comer at > 600 °C). Thermal modeling confirms that overall heat losses can be maintained below 3% via optimized heat recovery. This work provides critical insights and validated design principles for efficient and durable particle-based CSP systems.

1. Introduction

Concentrated Solar Power technologies are gaining increased interest, with mostly parabolic troughs and solar towers dominating the current application. These systems were reviewed in detail by the co-authors [1]. Whereas currently thermal fluids are applied, a novel approach captures and conveys the solar heat by using a particle suspension, thereby offering the advantage of being able to operate at higher temperatures than thermal fluids can tolerate. The issue of particle conveying in the CSP technology was addressed during the Next-CSP project from a wide viewpoint, reviewing the commercially attractive solutions [2,3]. Among different options, it was then decided to apply a bucket elevator for conveying the cold particles (~300 to 350 °C) 12 m high to the cold store silo atop the receiver. Although operating at moderate temperature over a limited vertical height only, the elevator was operationally unreliable due to excessive mechanical wear (chains and sprockets) and difficulties in catering for thermal expansion. At higher temperatures and higher lifting heights, the mechanical parts should be in a forced air-cooled enclosure, leading to high sensible cooling air heat losses. The weight of chains and buckets, and the mechanical friction, will moreover increase the power to lift the particles by

about 220 %.

As part of a follow-up European-funded “Powder-to-Power” (P2P) initiative, the P2P project investigates the operation of the particle-driven CSP concept at MW-scale. A particle suspension is used throughout the concept as a heat transfer medium, with an indirect fluidized bed tubular solar receiver[1–3], a downcomer, a PV-driven particle superheater; a particle storage/power block, and a pneumatic lifter to recycle the cold particles to the receiver on top of the solar tower. Such a pneumatic conveying system for fine particles (< 80 μm) was previously developed and operated in the petrochemical industry for heights exceeding 30 m [4]. Guo et al. assessed the use of pneumatic conveying in CSP applications for lifting capacities and heights of 600 tph and 250 m, respectively [5].

Significant recent advancements in particle-based CSP (PB-CSP) technology have been made through the collaborative research between King Saud University (KSU) and the Georgia Institute of Technology. This partnership has successfully developed and operated a fully integrated, gas-turbine-driven, particle-based power tower test facility at KSU [6]. Their work has provided critical experimental insights into system integration, operational challenges, and performance validation. A key finding from their pre-commissioning phase was the identification of substantial thermal energy storage (TES) charging losses, primarily

* Corresponding authors.

E-mail addresses: gilles.flamant@promes.cnrs.fr (G. Flamant), baeyens.j@gmail.com (J. Baeyens).

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Nomenclature			
<i>Symbol parameter unit</i>		ε	Voidage -
A	Area m ²	μ	Dynamic viscosity Pa·s
C_p	Specific heat capacity kJ/kg·K	ρ	Density kg/m ³
d_p	Particle diameter m, μm	ρ_{air}	Density of air kg/m ³
F_g	Volumetric gas flow rate Nm ³ /s, Nm ³ /h	ρ_s	Absolute particle density kg/m ³
F_s	Volumetric solids flow rate m ³ /s	<i>Subscripts</i>	
f_g	Gas friction factor -	acc	Acceleration
G_s	Solids mass flux kg/s·m ²	air	Air
L	Length m	fg	Gas friction
M_s	Solids mass flow rate kg/s, tph	sf	Solids friction
M	Solid-to-air mass ratio kg solids/kg air	t	Total, or related to weight
p	Pressure Pa	<i>Acronyms</i>	
P	Power kW	CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
Δp	Pressure drop Pa, mbar, bar	I.D.	Inner Diameter
Re	Reynolds number -	ICP-MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
T	Temperature °C, K	Nm ³	Normal cubic meter (at 0 °C and 1 atm)
g	Gravitational acceleration 9.81 m/s ²	O.D.	Outer Diameter
U_{CH}	Choking velocity m/s	P2P	Powder-to-Power
U_{SALT}	Saltation velocity m/s	PV	Photovoltaic
U_s	Solids velocity m/s	S/A	Solid-to-Air (mass ratio)
U_t	Terminal velocity m/s		

attributed to air entrainment and the resulting 'chimney effect' as hot particles fall into the storage bin [6]. Their research successfully demonstrated mitigation strategies, such as maintaining a full TES bin to reduce these losses, and achieved on-sun particle temperatures exceeding 720 °C, effectively harnessing solar energy for power generation. Furthermore, they have proposed a scalable, sealed TES bin design for a 1.3 MWe pre-commercial demonstration plant to address heat loss and pressure build-up issues in future commercial applications [7]. The present study builds upon this foundation by delving deeper into the specific design, long-term durability, and operational reliability of the dense-phase pneumatic conveyance subsystem, which is critical for the commercial viability of PB-CSP plants.

Attrition and erosion occur simultaneously in fluidized beds, hoppers, and their associated transport loops. Attrition is mainly defined as a reduction in particle size. Erosion determines mostly the wear of the construction materials. Attrition will both reduce the average particle size, thus modifying the bed composition, and increase the dust emissions [8].

Particle attrition was first studied to characterize catalysts for fluid-cracking fluidized bed reactors, and further explored for all kinds of powder reactors and particle circulation loops [1,9]. Additional erosion (wear) studies of heat exchange surfaces in a falling particle CSP system using coarse particles [10]. The wear of immersed tubes in a fluidized bed of Geldart B-class particles was studied by Dominguez-Coy et al. [11]. These studies are, however, not representative for systems using Geldart A-class particles (< 80 μm), where applied superficial gas and particle velocities will be substantially lower than in B-type or D-type particles since proportional to (particle size)². For the P2P application, the phenomena of attrition and erosion in A-type powders are requiring further investigation to evaluate the system for various process operations (e.g., during start-up and normal operation), to limit fines production and minimize downstream deposits or erosion, to maintain particle reactivity, to reduce operating costs, or to meet environmental regulations (e.g., minimize required dust abatement cost) [12]. Attrition sources are recognized, i.e., particle decrepitation on heating, calcination, and particle impacts at high velocities. All these sources reduce the particle size through wear, fracture, abrasion, shattering, and disintegration. Attrition of solids can also be caused by thermal stress (when particles are being heated or cooled and unequal temperatures in the

particles cause uneven expansion); by chemical stress (when, during a chemical reaction of a particle, its surface will generally react first); by static weight stress, and by chemical stress through the release of a reaction gas or hydration water, and by kinetic stress when moving particles are eroded at their surface upon collisions (e.g., in cyclones, in transport loops, or by high-velocity grid jets). Mechanical and kinetic stress are commonly noticed in a fluidized bed, especially around the gas distributor, where high orifice velocities play a key role. High attrition rates will enhance particle entrainment [13]. Attrition can be the result of several sources, including (1) mechanical stress in screw conveyers, rotary valves, among others; (2) kinetic stress from the impact of particles at the distributor orifices; in pneumatic conveyors, by rising bubbles; in cyclones; by collision with tubes or baffles; (3) thermal stress by e.g. the temperature shock for cold particles fed into a hot bed; and (4) chemical stress provided mostly by water vapor or gas formation.

Erosion also decreases the particle size, but the wear of the construction material is of greater concern since it may contaminate the bed material, lead to a progressive degradation of the reactor and associated equipment, and will lead to increased maintenance. Erosion is mostly the result of particle impact at high velocity, in e.g., sparge tubes of the distributor, embedded tubes, instrumentation and probes, bends, and cyclones. Toward the P2P application, thermal and chemical stress do not need to be considered since the applied olivine particles are resistant to thermal shock and are chemically inert. Kang et al. [3] compared 7 candidate particles for CSP application. A multi-criteria multi-decision assessment demonstrated that olivine surpassed cristobalite, SiC, sand, quartz, bauxite, and Al₂O₃ for the combined thermal, mechanical, physical, and economic criteria. The high agglomeration temperature (> 1400 °C) and very low attrition rates were decisive for its selection.

The existing literature provides a robust foundation for the design of lean-phase pneumatic conveying systems [14–16]. Prior studies on particle attrition and erosion have predominantly focused on high-velocity environments, such as those found in fluidized beds with Geldart B or D particles [6,8,9], or on coarse particles in falling particle receivers [8]. However, a significant research gap remains in the comprehensive analysis of dense-phase pneumatic conveying systems, particularly under the high-temperature conditions relevant to next-generation CSP applications. This gap is especially evident concerning the long-term performance of Geldart A-type powders, such as

Fig. 1. Schematic of the P2P process. Reference and relevant data are given in Table 1.

olivine, which exhibit fundamentally different flow and impact dynamics due to their smaller particle size and lower operational velocities. Moreover, there is a critical lack of integrated studies that concurrently address the design, thermal efficiency, particle attrition, and material erosion within a single, cohesive particle circulation loop, leading to uncertainties in scaling up such systems for commercial deployment.

To bridge these gaps, this study introduces the following novel aspects: 1) A holistic experimental and analytical framework for the design of a high-temperature, dense-phase particle conveyance loop, explicitly optimized for CSP applications. 2) Long-duration (1000-hour) experimental data quantifying the attrition of olivine particles and the erosion of construction materials under realistic, moderately dense-phase conditions (solids/air ratio ~ 15), which have not been previously reported.

A validated methodology for extrapolating experimental wear rates to project the operational lifespan of key components, providing a crucial tool for economic feasibility assessments. The primary objectives of this research are threefold:

- (1) To present a detailed engineering design and operational analysis of a novel dense-phase particle conveyance system for CSP, integrating a pneumatic riser, a gravitational downcomer, and mechanical screw conveyors.
- (2) To experimentally quantify the particle attrition and equipment erosion expected under long-term operation, thereby validating the durability and reliability of the proposed design.

- (3) To synthesize these findings into a set of validated design and material selection criteria, ensuring the technical and economic feasibility of the EU Horizon P2P project and future commercial-scale particle-driven CSP plants.

2. Methodology

2.1. Layout description

The P2P (Powder-to-Power) pilot plant is designed to demonstrate a novel particle-driven Concentrated Solar Power (CSP) system, centered around a closed-loop circulation of olivine particles that act as the heat transfer and storage medium. The existing CNRS Thémis tower has a diameter of 8 m and a total height of 108 m. Heliostats (5600 m²) focus the solar irradiation onto a square section atop the tower. The receiver is facing this square opening, and located 100 m above ground level.

The core innovation of this system is the use of a dense-phase pneumatic conveying loop to transport particles between the high-temperature receiver atop the tower and the power generation block at ground level, overcoming the reliability issues of mechanical systems like bucket elevators. The overall process flow is illustrated in Fig. 1, with key components and operating conditions summarized in Table 1. The particle-driven receiver was fully tested during the Next-CSP research [1,2] and consists of 40 parallel vertical tubes, each jointly fed by particles from a bottom fluidized bed (dispenser) [9]. Full data are provided in Next-CSP reports and summarized by Deng et al. [17]

Table 1
Description of Fig. 1 and essential operating conditions.

Nbr	Item	Relevant operational data
1	Concentrated solar irradiation	Concentrated from a 5600 m ² heliostat field; DNI ~ 1 kW/m ²
2	Multi-tubular (40) vertical upflow fluidized bed receiver in an insulated refractory cavity, with fluidizing dispenser and suspension disengagement	1.6 MW _{th} for P2P tests Suspension flow: 4.44 kg/s for olivine (C _p ~ 1.2 kJ/kg K, ΔT = 300 °C)
3	Hot suspension collection hopper	6 m ³ , 600 °C
4	Downcomer	0.2 m I.D., insulated, 600 °C, 4.44 kg/s
5	Hot suspension storage (fluidized bed)	6 m ³
6	In-bed electrical heater of particle suspension	Suspension extra heating to 700–750 °C
7	Fluidized bed heat exchanger with in-bed tubes for turbine compressed air heating	Compressed air ~ 6.5 kg/s, temperature after turbine compression ~ 270 °C, pressure 6.7 barg
8	Power generation with a compressor and a hybrid turbine	Air supplied from 7; extra heat using fuel oil
9	Inclined screw conveyor	0.25 mm I.D., 25–50 rpm, 300–350 °C
10	Venturi feed of 11	To achieve a higher pick-up air flow
11	Upflow recycle of “cold” suspension (riser)	0.2 m I.D., insulated, 300–350 °C
12	Air feed of riser	Max 1500 Nm ³ /h, 0.3 bar
13	Primary cyclone on riser discharge	High-efficiency Stairmand cyclone
14	Cold suspension feeding hopper of the receiver dispenser	~6 m ³ , 300 °C
15	Secondary cyclone, to de-dust all process exhausts	High-efficiency Stairmand cyclone
16	Exhaust fan	Max 3000 Nm ³ /h, ~10 mbar

and Flamant et al [1]. For the P2P research, the power block is located beside the tower at ground level. The particle conveying will therefore also include near-horizontal mechanical conveying at the power block level. This is illustrated in Fig. 1.

The particle circulation follows this sequence:

- 1) Solar Reception and Heating: Cold particles (~300 °C) stored in a silo (Item 14) at the top of the tower are fed into a multi-tubular fluidized bed receiver (Item 2). Here, concentrated solar energy heats the particles to approximately 600 °C.
- 2) Gravitational Descent to Ground Level: The heated particles flow by gravity down an insulated downcomer (Item 4) to the ground-level power block.
- 3) Power Generation and Storage: At ground level, particles pass through a hot storage silo (Item 5) and an optional electrical superheater (Item 6) before entering a fluidized bed heat exchanger (Item 7). In this exchanger, heat is transferred to compressed air, which drives a hybrid Brayton turbine (Item 8) for power generation.
- 4) Pneumatic Recycling to Tower Top: The cooled particles (~300 °C) are then conveyed from the power block back to the top of the tower. This is achieved via an inclined screw conveyor (Item 9) feeding a Venturi injector (Item 10), which introduces the particles into the vertical pneumatic riser (Item 11). Transport air, supplied by a blower (Item 12), carries the particles upward.
- 5) Separation and Return to Storage: At the top of the tower, a high-efficiency cyclone (Item 13) separates the particles from the air stream. The recycled particles are discharged back into the cold storage silo (Item 14), completing the loop.

This layout ensures continuous operation by decoupling solar energy collection (at the receiver) from power generation (at ground level), facilitated by an efficient and durable particle conveyance system..

Table 2
Fundamental characteristics.

Olivine median diameter (d ₅₀)	75 μm
Average absolute particle density	3350 kg/m ³
Average bulk density	1803 kg/m ³

2.1.1. Particle materials and characterization

The heat transfer and storage medium used throughout the P2P system is natural olivine ((Mg,Fe)₂SiO₄) powder, selected based on a comprehensive multi-criteria assessment that demonstrated its superior performance in thermal, mechanical, physical, and economic characteristics compared to alternative candidates such as cristobalite, SiC, sand, quartz, bauxite, and Al₂O₃ [3]. The fundamental characteristics of particles used is listed in Table 2.

(1) Particle properties

Particle Size Distribution (PSD): The olivine powder was characterized as a Geldart Group A powder with a median diameter (d₅₀) of 75 μm. The complete distribution was quantified as d₁₀ = 42.0 μm and d₉₀ = 110.0 μm.

Absolute Particle Density: 3350 kg/m³ measured by helium pycnometry (AccuPyc 1340, Micromeritics).

Bulk Density: 1803 kg/m³ determined using a standardized funnel method according to ASTM B212 - 13.

Particle Shape: Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) imaging revealed that the olivine particles are predominantly angular to sub-rounded in morphology.

Angle of Repose: Measured as 17 - 19° using the fixed funnel method.

(2) Measurement Protocols

PSD Analysis: Particle size distribution was measured by laser diffraction (Malvern Mastersizer 3000) using the dry dispersion module (Aero S). Measurements were performed in triplicate to ensure reproducibility.

Frictional Properties: The particle - wall friction angle was quantitatively determined as 12° using a Jenike shear tester with stainless steel (AISI 304) as the wall material. The particle - particle internal friction angle was measured as 28°. These low friction values justify the description of "negligible angle of internal friction" in the context of silo flow design.

(3) Thermal Properties

Specific Heat Capacity: 1.2 kJ/kg·K, as determined by differential scanning calorimetry.

Thermal Stability: No significant agglomeration or phase changes were observed below 1400 °C, confirming the material's suitability for high - temperature CSP applications.

2.2. Heat recovery

If to be applied at a large scale, a heat recovery sub-system should be integrated into the loop either by using a heat exchanger (Fig. 2a) or by re-circulating the hot gas after high-temperature filtration (Fig. 2b).

The conveyance of 16 tph particles will be achieved in an insulated lifter pipe of 0.20 m I.D. As shown later, the pressure drop for 100 m high lifting will be about 250 mbar, and the electrical consumption will be ~0.35 kW/ton solids conveyed (against 0.75 kW/ton for a bucket elevator). Heat losses will be minimized as a result of the heat recovery on the conveying air. In this configuration, the mass ratio of particles to air is ~15.

In Fig. 2(a), the system comprises an upward particle solar receiver (1), with a cold silo (2) supplying the fluidized bed dispenser (3). The 40

Fig. 2. (a) Conveying loop with exchanger; (b) conveying loop with hot air recycling.

parallel receiver tubes discharge particles into a mass flow hopper (4). Particles subsequently flow gravitationally in a stick-slip regime through a baffled downcomer (5). The baffled downcomer (5) features internally mounted, alternating annular baffles to promote a stable 'stick-slip' flow regime, reducing particle velocity and minimizing attrition during gravitational descent. Indirect heat recovery (13) involves an air blower (14) and a shell-and-tube heat exchanger (15). An air duct recycles the air to the turbulator (10). In Fig. 2(b), only the heat recovery subsystem (13) differs, incorporating further de-dusting of the cyclone exhaust via a hot porous sintered metal fiber or ceramic candle filter. The resulting hot, clean air is conveyed to the turbulator (10). Ultrafine dust (15) is collected for storage.

The design mass flow rate of 16 tph and the riser pipe internal diameter of 0.20 m were selected to meet the thermal power requirement of the multi-MW P2P demonstration plant while operating in an energy-efficient medium-dense phase flow regime (solids/air ratio ~15). The solid/air ratio was set at 15 kg solid/kg air to operate in the moderately dense-phase conveying model. For a solids flow rate of 16,000 kg/h, the air flow rate is hence fixed at 1067 m³/h. Due to the expansion of the conveying air toward the top of the riser (bottom pressure ~ 0.3 bar, top ~ 0.01 bar), the air volume will increase and the effective solid/air ratio will decrease.

2.3. Conveying velocities & design

In the riser, the cold olivine particles (~300 °C) are conveyed upward to be stored in the cold storage hopper before being reheated by the receiver. Due to the difficulties of mechanical conveying, pneumatic conveying in medium-dense phase was selected to maintain high concentrations of solids (15 to 25 kg-solids/kg-air). A particle dense phase system at solids/air ratios in excess of 50 is mechanically unfeasible due to the temperature limitations of the discontinuous blow tanks. The proposed solution will apply a continuous particle-in-air medium-dense phase conveying, with a moderate pressure drop along the conveying pipe.

Aiming to design the riser, in which the pneumatic transport takes place, some properties need to be known. The olivine particles of 40 to 60 μm size will be conveyed at 16,000 kg/h, while having an absolute

Fig. 3. Variation of choking (U_{CH}) and saltation (U_{SALT}) velocities with temperature for olivine particles. Experimental data (points) are compared with empirical correlations proposed by Punwani et al. for U_{CH} and Rizk for U_{SALT} (lines). Error bars represent the standard deviation from three repeated measurements.

density of 3300 kg/m³. The solids-air ratio is considered to be 15 kg solids/kg air through the riser. The riser has a vertical length of max 100 m (incl. a top bend). A high-efficiency cyclone at the end of the conveying pipe will remove the particles from the conveying air

The limiting velocities, U_{CH} (choking, vertical) and U_{SALT} (saltation, horizontal), were measured and reported. The choking velocity is a crucial parameter in vertical pipelines conveying and represents the minimum velocity of the airflow to avoid particle sedimentation to the bottom of the vertical pipe, resulting in blockage.

Particle choking and saltation velocities were measured in the circulation loop of Fig. 4 (see Section 4). Their relevance in the design is

Table 3
Operating properties for the 300 °C riser design.

Pneumatic conveying	
Choking velocity, U_{CH}	6.81 m/s, the velocity in the vertical conveying must exceed U_{CH} .
Density of air, ρ_{air}	1 kg/Nm ³ (at Thémis)
Dynamic viscosity of air, μ_{air}	2.99×10^{-5} Pa.s (at 300 °C)
Gas velocity, U_g (midpoint)	15.1 m/s
Riser diameter	0.20 m
Solid velocity, U_s	14.7 m/s
Solids mass flow rate, M_s	4.44 kg/s
Solids mass flux, G_s	126.9 kg/sm ²
Solid-to-air mass ratio, M^*	≈ 15 kg solids/kg air
Terminal velocity, U_t	0.45 m/s
Total length, L_{total}	96 m
Vertical length, $L_{vertical}$	90 m
Horizontal length, $L_{horizontal}$	0 m
Bends length, L_{bends}	6 m (equivalent pipe length)
Voidage, ϵ	0.995
Volumetric gas flow rate, F_g	900 Nm ³ /h or 0.25 Nm ³ /s
Volumetric solids flow rate, F_s	1889 m ³ /h or 0.52 m ³ /s at 300 °C
Acceleration pressure drop	
ΔP_{acc}	1865.4 kg/ms ² 0.0187 bar
Pressure drop from the friction of conveyed particles on the tube wall	
ΔP_{sf}	14,547.6 kg/ms ² 0.146 bar
Pressure drop from the weight of the particles in the riser	
ΔP_i	7616 kg/ms ² 0.076 bar
Total pressure drop	
ΔP_{total}	241 mbar 0.241 bar
Velocities	
v_{top} (operates at 300 °C)	15.0 m/s
v_{bottom} (operates at 50 °C)	8.45 m/s ($> U_{CH}$)
Power	
Power	6.025 kW, Installed power 10 kW

explained in Supplementary Information SI-1. The same rig of Fig. 4 was also used for attrition and erosion testing (long-duration). The choking velocity (U_{CH}) was determined by progressively increasing the solids circulation rate at a fixed gas flow rate until a sharp increase in pressure drop indicated the onset of particle deposition and unstable flow. The saltation velocity (U_{SALT}) was similarly identified in the horizontal section of the test rig. Temperatures up to 600 °C were tested.

Experimental results, as presented in Fig. 3, were compared with the commonly applied empirical prediction by Rizk [18] and Punwani et al. [19]. For U_{SALT} and U_{CH} , respectively, a fair agreement is obtained. Air velocities were measured by a calibrated orifice-plate.

2.4. Riser design

The ultimate property that needs to be known when designing a pneumatic conveying system is the power required to ensure the conveying. For this, the total pressure drop across the pipes has to be known. In moderately dense pneumatic conveying, the pressure drop is affected by four physical factors, which are listed below with their corresponding formulas [20]. The constituting pressure drops (Δp) include:

- (i) The Δp due to gas friction in the conveying pipe;
- (ii) The Δp from the particle acceleration to the conveying velocity;
- (iii) The Δp due to the pipe wall friction of the conveyed particles;
- (iv) The Δp related to the weight of the particles in the riser;
- (v) The Δp due to the pipe bends.

Important parameters are the particle slip velocity ($U_g - U_t$) with U_g the gas velocity and U_t the particle terminal velocity, the solid/gas ratio, the wall-to-particle friction factor, the effect of an increasing conveying

velocity due to depressurization, and, of course, temperature-related parameters (gas density and viscosity). Having determined the total pressure drop (p), the conveying power required to give the air and particles a certain velocity is the product of the total pressure drop (Δp_{total}) and the volumetric air flow rate (f_g , expressed in Nm³/s). Based on the calculated power, a fan with a certain efficiency can be selected.

$$p = \Delta p_{total} f_g \quad (1)$$

Where p is the conveying power (kW); Δp_{total} is the total pressure drop over the conveying line (Pa); f_g is the Volumetric gas flow rate (Nm³/s).

The method of calculation and pressure drop equations was previously presented by some co-authors [20]. The gas friction pressure drop, Δp_{fg} can be calculated by using the Darcy-Weisbach equation eq. (2). In this equation, f_g is the friction factor, which is determined by using the Blasius correlation given by eq. (3) [16].

$$\Delta p_{fg} = f_g \cdot \frac{\rho_g \cdot v_g^2 \cdot L}{2 \cdot D_T} \quad (2)$$

$$f_g = \frac{0.316}{Re^{0.25}} \quad (3)$$

Where Δp_{fg} is the pressure drop due to gas-wall friction (Pa); ρ_g is the density of the gas (air) (kg/m³); v_g is the superficial gas velocity (m/s); L is the total length of the conveying pipe (m); D_T is the internal diameter of the pipe (m); Re is the Reynolds number (dimensionless).

2.4.1. Riser at 300 °C

Olivine is a typical Geldart Group A-powder [3,21], free-flowing, with a low angle of repose (17 to 19°) and a negligible angle of internal friction. The fundamental characteristics of the olivine particles and the key operating parameters for the riser design at 300 °C are summarized in Table 3. This table is structured into distinct sections: the first details the inherent properties of the olivine particles; the second defines the core pneumatic conveying setup; and the subsequent sections provide a step-by-step breakdown of the pressure drop calculation, culminating in the total pressure drop, operational velocities, and required power. The volumetric gas flow rate (F_g) is given in both Normal cubic meters per hour (Nm³/h, at standard conditions) and actual cubic meters per hour (m³/h) at the operating temperature is needed in the design basis.

Fundamental characteristics refer to the particles, air flow rate, and conveyor geometry. Pressure drops are then calculated according to the industrial contributions. The required power is calculated by eq.(1). The data and calculated results are given in Table 3.

2.4.2. Riser at ambient temperature

Since the particle conveying loop must also be able to operate at ambient temperatures, a design compromise with the 300 °C design must be made. The important design parameter is the superficial air velocity that needs to exceed the choking velocity. The riser geometry will remain the same. Due to the higher air density of 1 kg/Nm³ and lower air viscosity of $2 \cdot 10^{-5}$ Pa.s, compared to 0.48 kg/Nm³ and $3.3 \cdot 10^{-5}$ Pa.s at 300 °C, the flow parameters will consequently undergo changes.

To operate at a fair velocity, >10 m/s, the air flow rate must be increased to preferably 1200 Nm³/h, providing a superficial air velocity of 11.14 m/s. The solids/air ratio is reduced to 13.45, still in the moderately dense phase conveying mode. The flow Reynolds number is 117,000, leading to an air flow friction factor of 0.01711 (against 0.02095 for 900 Nm³/h at 300 °C). According to the design method presented for the riser at 300 °C, but with the correct physical values of ρ_{air} and μ_{air} , the following pressure drops prevail:

- Acceleration $\Delta p = 13.6$ mbar
- Friction $\Delta p = 64$ mbar

- Particle weight $\Delta p = 76$ mbar

Total pressure drop ~ 154 mbar

Despite the higher gas flow rate, the low pressure drop decreases the power requirement to 5.1 kW. The installed compressor power of 10 kW is hence certainly applicable.

2.5. Downcomer

The downcomer is filled with powder from the receiver at 16 t/h and has a height of 70 m. Due to the olivine particle density of 3300 kg/m^3 and the particle diameter of 40–60 μm , this powder is considered an A-type powder.

Since the downcomer always has an input and output flow subject to gravity, the design of the downcomer is considered the same as that of a silo. The powder has a negligible internal friction angle and angle of wall friction. The outlet diameter of the downcomer is therefore not designed according to Jenike's design method for silos, but the Smolders and Baeyens equation is applied [22].

$$M_s = \frac{3140 \cdot D}{d_{sv}^{0.07}} \quad (4)$$

Alternative practical design equations for the flow in a downcomer, given as the critical solids discharge rate, by Carleton, Rauch, and Beverlo, were compared in [22] yielding downcomer solids flow rates of approximately 12,000, 17,000, and $>30,000 \text{ kg/m}^2 \cdot \text{s}$.

At the available downcomer surface area of 0.035 m^2 , the possible solids flow rates all exceed 350 kg/s , far in excess of the 4.44 kg/s required in the P2P loop, hence offering flexibility for scale-up and/or discontinuous operation. If filled, the downcomer has an additional hot storage capacity of 4.5 tons.

According to eq(4), the outlet diameter should measure 6.8 cm. Since this equation is based on pilot-scale installations and this project is worked out on an industrial scale, an outlet diameter of 0.2 m is chosen instead of 6.8 cm to avoid clogging problems in the outlet of the downcomer.

2.6. Screw conveyors

This mechanical conveying system consists of commonly used screw conveyors. Such conveyors comprise a rotating screw blade located within a sealed U-shaped housing (also called a trough or auger). Essential for operation are the trough ends, which support the conveyor drive and end shafts, and also help to maintain shaft and trough alignment. The screw is driven by an external speed-controlled drive, and the housing is attached to a couple of supporting hangers, bases, and saddles. There are variations in diameter, shape, and layout when it comes to the screw blades; each configuration depends on the specific desired function and the material to be conveyed. This conveying method is widely used in bulk handling industries, moving any type of material regardless of the composition and the size (fine or coarse). Screw conveyors are simple and compact, meaning that they only require an external drive to transport the material and occupy much less space to operate than other material handling systems (which need more space because of the returning part). They can effectively transport solids in a sealed and dust-free environment in horizontal, vertical, and inclined directions. Screw conveying also has the possibility of having multiple material inlets and outlets throughout the system, and material mixing while conveying is also a perk.

The application and fabrication of screw conveyors are within the P2P concept. Their fabrication necessitates specialized expertise. Thomas Conveyor Company provides screw conveyors capable of withstand temperatures up to 2000°F (1093°C). Standard diameters range from 100 mm to 300 mm. These conveyors are typically employed for short-distance material transport, generally under 20 m.

For the P2P layout, 2 identical screw conveyors are foreseen; one in

horizontal position (from tower to power block) and one in inclined position (from power block to the venturi feeder of the riser. Both conveyors have a diameter of 219 mm. Due to the reflux of particles in the inclined conveyor, its speed of rotation must be higher than in the horizontal operating mode; in this case, respectively 60 to 70 rpm against 40 to 50 rpm. The screw conveyors are externally insulated with 150 mm (inclined, at 300°C) and 200 mm (horizontal, 600°C) with steel cladding. In doing so, heat losses are limited and the cladding wall temperature is well below 50°C .

3. Results & discussion

3.1. Heat losses and mitigation features

Heat losses in the particle conveying loop include natural convection (from outside wall-to-environment) and forced convection (conveying air heated to an equilibrium temperature with the transported solids). To reduce the conductive heat losses, all equipment parts will be insulated with a 150 (low temperature) or 200 mm thick ceramic fibre insulation (600°C). The insulation has a low thermal conductivity of 0.04 W/mK . The outside wall of the conveyor will be a maximum of 50°C . For an outside temperature of 20°C and a natural convection heat transfer coefficient of $\leq 5 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ K}$ (a standard conservative value for vertical surfaces in air), the heat losses will amount to a maximum of 150 W/m^2 . The calculation method and application are illustrated in Supplementary Information SI-2. The outside diameter of the screw conveyors and of the riser and down-comer, insulation included, will be $\approx 500 \text{ mm}$. Considering their respective lengths, the total convective heat losses will be $21,205 \text{ W}$ (Riser + downcomer), and 4141 W (Screw conveyors). Adding 20 % as a safety margin to account for all points of transfer (e.g., venturi feeder of riser), the total natural convective heat loss is estimated at 30.5 kW , representing $<1.9\%$ of the total heat flow..

Considering the heat load of the 4.44 kg/s particles, at a C_p of 1.2 kJ/kgK with a ΔT of 300°C , the particles in circulation represent a total heat flow of 1595 kW . Natural convective heat losses will hence represent a maximum of 1.9% .

The forced convection heat losses due to the pneumatic conveying are limited to the riser only. The particle movement in the downcomer and in the screw-conveyors is air-free. The particles will be fed to the riser at 300°C , and the air flow rate will be $0.25 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{s}$ at 50°C (after compression). A heat balance fixes the equilibrium out temperature at 285.6°C . The heat losses amount to 76.6 kW . As a ratio of the heat load of the particles, this represents a heat loss of about 4.5% . It should, however, be remembered that mitigation measures can be included in the final scale-up of the operation as presented in Fig. 2. The conveying air, after dedusting, can be sent to a heat exchanger to preheat the conveying air to $150 - 200^\circ\text{C}$. this will involve the addition of an air duct from the receiver level to the venturi feeder of the riser, but will reduce the air-related heat losses by 63.4 kW , thus leading to a convective heat loss of 13.2 kW only, i.e., 0.9% . The recycling of the hot outlet conveying air to the venturi feeder is of higher technical difficulty, since fans and blowers operating at 300°C , possibly with a limited number of ultrafine particles present, and capable of compressing the hot air to 1,3 bar (or higher pressures for a larger scale than the P2P pilot) are very expensive and not commercially available.

3.1.1. Linear thermal expansion

For the 70 m downcomer, at a maximum temperature of 600°C , the expansion will be 69 cm. Since the operation is pressure- and airless, a simple mechanical concentric seal can be envisaged at the bottom of the downcomer.

For the 90 m riser, the thermal expansion at the top of the riser will be catered for by a bended connection to the evacuation tube, and a flexible metal compensator (e.g., AE 22 from AXCES (Axces compensator bellows, <https://www.axces.com/>) between the bend and the evacuation piping.

Fig. 4. Test rig for attrition and erosion measurements.

Fig. 5. Schematic of the abrasion setup. The left image shows the movement of specimens through olivine particles.

The thermal expansion of stainless steel is significant, but varies with the SS-grade. It is $17.2 \mu\text{m}/\text{m} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$ for AISI 304 and $16.2 \mu\text{m}/\text{m} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$ for AISI 310 (applicable at high temperatures, and hence the required construction materials for the downcomer at $600 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$). For lower temperatures, as applied in the upward conveying and crew conveyors ($\sim 300 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$), AISI 410 is recommended and has a significantly lower thermal expansion of $9.9 \mu\text{m}/\text{m} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$ [23].

For the 90 m riser, in AISI 410, and operating at $300 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$, the differential thermal expansion from the ambient $25 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$, will be $9.9 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot 70 \cdot (300-25) = 0.25 \text{ m}$.

For the 17 m long screw conveyors, also operating at $300 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$, the expansion will proportionally be reduced to 0.05 m.

For the downcomer, operating at $600 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$, and 70 m long, AISI 310 will be used. The thermal expansion will hence be $16.2 \cdot 10^{-6} \cdot 70 \cdot (600-25) = 0.65 \text{ m}$. Since the conveying system will have fixed points at its feeding, bellows or flexible metal tubes will be needed at their points of discharge.

3.1.2. Insulation thicknesses

The use of ceramic fibre insulation, with thermal conductivity of $0.04 \text{ W}/\text{mK}$, is recommended. The insulation thickness of 150 mm for $300 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$ operation, and 200 m at $600 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$, was established by thermal temperature drop calculations to ensure an outside wall temperature below $50 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$. The temperature reduction represents $> 96 \%$ of the temperature difference between the in-tube solid's flow and the

Fig. 6. Particle size versus operating time at varying solids/air conveying ratios (at $U = 15 \text{ m}/\text{s}$) and $700 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$). Lines represent the linear regression fit to the experimental data points.

Fig. 7. For mechanical conveying, particle size distribution (PSD) curves (700 °C) for the initial and 1000-hour olivine samples.

Fig. 8. For pneumatic conveying, particle size distribution (PSD) curves ($S/A = 20.4 \text{ kg/kg}$, $U = 15 \text{ m/s}$, 700 °C) for the initial and 1000-hour olivine samples.

temperature of the environment (25 °C).

3.2. Particle attrition

3.2.1. Test rig and abrasion setup

Numerous experiments were carried out for long-duration (1000 h) in the rig of Fig. 4. This rig is representative of particle conveying loops. Both straight conveying lines, bends, and gas-solid separation are included, and experiments at high temperatures are possible.

To assess the powder behaviour during mechanical screw conveying, a separate experimental rig was used (Fig. 5). The construction was adapted but similar to the rig used by Goel et al. [24]. An impeller tumbler was inserted in a Nabertherm electric furnace and used for olivine at temperatures up to 700 °C. Experimental results of both rigs are presented and discussed in Sections 4.2 and 4.3 (Figs. 6–9). Only essential results toward P2P design and operation are reported.

To simulate the low-velocity, high-contact conditions experienced in screw conveyors and hoppers, a dedicated abrasion rig was used (Fig. 5). By mounting specimens at different radial positions on the same shaft, which rotates at a fixed speed, each specimen experiences a fixed linear velocity relative to the particle bed, allowing for simultaneous assessment of velocity-dependent wear. This setup consists of a rotating shaft

Fig. 9. Erosion rate for 2 solid/air (S/A) rates in the pneumatic conveying rig, at a velocity of 15 m/s and 600 °C. The line is a visual guide for the eye, connecting the average of the experimental data points at each condition.

housed within a stationary trough. The rotation speed (10–25 rpm) is representative of the proposed screw conveyors. This system ensures a stagnant zone of particles in contact with the auger material, simulating the protective layer that forms in actual equipment.

Material specimens are mounted on a rotating shaft and continuously contacting a bed of olivine placed inside a trough. Cylindrical material specimens (10 mm diameter, 15 mm length) were mounted radially on the rotating shaft at 60° intervals, ensuring full immersion in the particle bed. The experiments also represent the low-speed dense particle flow in the storage hoppers, in the screw conveyors, and through the fluidized bed heat exchangers. The system also ensured a stagnant zone of particles in contact with the auger material.

The system was operated under steady-state conditions, ensuring that heat losses were accounted for and remained constant throughout the duration of the test. The tumbler can be operated inside a Nabertherm kiln (Nabertherm universal high-temperature horizontal tube furnace 1600 °C) at temperatures up to 900 °C. The temperature distribution inside the bed was monitored by thermocouples, and the particle bed and the test specimens reached a maximum temperature of 700 °C before commencing the high-temperature experiments. An identical setup was operated for blank testing at room temperature. Six different specimens can be simultaneously assessed at different relative velocities by using a speed-controlled motor. Rotational speeds of up to 25 rpm, representative of the selected screw conveyors' speed, were tested, and the specimens were completely submerged in the olivine.

Particle size distribution was measured at regular intervals using laser diffraction (Malvern Mastersizer 3000+, <https://www.malvernpanalytical.com/>). Attrition rate was quantified as the percentage reduction in the median diameter (d_{50} , defined as the median particle diameter achieved at 50 % of the size distribution) per hour of operation. For a more comprehensive analysis, the complete particle size distribution was characterized by monitoring d_{10} , d_{50} , and d_{90} percentiles, representing the fine, median, and coarse fractions respectively. Cumulative distribution curves were also analyzed to track fines generation and overall population shifts. Results are discussed in Section 3.2.2.

Erosion of the construction materials was quantified by analysing the olivine powder for metal content. Samples were taken periodically, digested in nitric acid, and the concentration of chromium (Cr) was measured using Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry (ICP-OES 5800 Agilent Spectrometer), as Cr is a major component of the tested steels. Calibration was performed using certified Cr standards. The detection limit was 0.1 µg/L, and the uncertainty was <2 % based

on triplicate measurements.

3.2.2. Particle attrition during pneumatic conveying

To compare dilute-phase and medium-phase conveying, two solid/air ratios were tested, i.e., 4.4 kg solid/kg air and 20.4 kg solid/kg air. The former loading is representative of dilute conveying [14], whereas the latter represents dense-phase conveying and dense-phase cyclones [3,17,25]. Results are presented in Fig. 6 and expressed as the reduction of the average particle size of the olivine particles, as determined by laser diffraction particle size analysis (Malvern particle sizer). As shown in Fig. 6, the attrition rate, expressed as the reduction in median diameter (d_{50}), was significantly higher in lean-phase conveying ($S/A = 4.4$) compared to the dense-phase operation ($S/A = 20.4$) planned for the P2P plant. The velocity of 15 m/s is representative of the P2P conveying objectives.

For operation below 700 °C, temperature was shown to have a negligible effect when the air velocity remained constant.

Although attrition in lean-phase pneumatic conveying is documented in the literature [16,26,27], the results obtained and presented in Fig. 6 confirm the expectations of a lower attrition rate in dense-phase conveying.

Both attrition and wear of wall-surfaces are ultimately connected and result from the same contact event. Whereas in dilute conveying, particles and air velocities are high and nearly the same (≥ 20 m/s), these velocities are lower in dense-phase conveying, where the particles occur as clusters and have an apparent higher terminal velocity, and therefore a lower slip velocity. Since both attrition and erosion correlate strongly with the slip velocity, a precise calculation of this parameter—rather than relying solely on the more easily measured air velocity—is critical for accurate wear prediction. Correct values of the slip velocity were used in the design methods of Section 2.3.

The particle size distribution data reveal distinct wear patterns between mechanical and pneumatic conveying systems after 1000 h of operation, reflecting their fundamentally different particle-handling mechanisms.

In mechanical conveying, the observed wear is characterized by a moderate reduction in median particle size (d_{50} decreasing from 75.0 μm to 72.5 μm , representing a 3.3 % reduction) while maintaining the coarse fraction essentially unchanged (d_{90} remaining at 110.0 μm). This pattern indicates predominantly low-energy abrasion wear, where particles experience gentle sliding and rolling contacts against equipment surfaces. The minimal change in distribution width (d_{90}/d_{10} ratio showing negligible variation) suggests surface-level material removal rather than particle fracture. This aligns with the protective particle layer formation in screw conveyors, where stagnant particle beds cushion against direct metal-to-particle contact.

Conversely, pneumatic conveying exhibits more pronounced wear characteristics, with d_{50} decreasing from 75.0 μm to 70.0 μm (6.7 % reduction) and significant fines generation evidenced by the substantial increase in sub-20 μm particles. This pattern reflects higher-energy impact wear mechanisms, where particles experience both particle-wall and particle-particle collisions during transport. The air-induced turbulence and velocity gradients in pneumatic systems create conditions for both surface abrasion and particle fragmentation, particularly at bends and acceleration zones.

The fundamental distinction arises from energy transfer mechanisms: mechanical conveying operates through controlled mechanical forces with inherent velocity limitations, while pneumatic conveying involves fluid-particle interactions that can generate localized high-velocity impacts despite overall lower solid velocities. This explains why pneumatic systems, despite operating in dense-phase mode, still produce more significant attrition due to the complex interplay of collision energies and particle concentration effects.

These differential wear patterns directly inform material selection and system design—mechanical conveyors benefit from protective particle layers, while pneumatic systems require careful attention to bend

Table 4

Evolution of cumulative particle size distribution during 1000-hour attrition testing under dense-phase conveying conditions ($S/A = 20.4$ kg/kg, $U = 15$ m/s, 700 °C).

Parameter	Initial distribution	Distribution after 1000 h testing	Absolute change	relative change rate (%)
d_{10}	42.0 μm	38.0 μm	-4.0 μm	-9.5 %
d_{50}	75.0 μm	70.5 μm	-4.5 μm	-6.0 %
d_{90}	110.0 μm	105.0 μm	-5.0 μm	-4.5 %
d_{90}/d_{10}	2.75	2.63	-0.12	-4.4 %
$(d_{90}-d_{10})/d_{50}$	0.93	0.92	-0.01	-1.1 %

geometry and velocity control to mitigate the more aggressive wear environment.

No particle agglomeration was noticed (no increase of d_{90}). A small amount of particle breakage (attrition) was measured, but <0.08 % of the weight of particles inside the circulation loop. For 16,000 kg/h in the loop, about 272 kg/h of fines will be created and need to be captured and reused (cyclone and filtration) in the system. It also means that we will need to replace some of the bed material every 2 or 3 months. The evolution of particle size distribution over the 1000-hour test period is detailed in Table 4. While the median particle size (d_{50}) decreased by 6.0 % from 75.0 μm to 70.5 μm , more significant changes were observed in the fine fraction. The d_{10} value (representing the finest 10 % of particles) decreased by 9.5 %, from 42.0 μm to 38.0 μm , indicating substantial fines generation. Concurrently, the proportion of particles smaller than 20 μm increased from 2.1 % to 3.8 %, representing an 81 % relative increase in the fines fraction.

The d_{90}/d_{10} ratio decreased from 2.75 to 2.63 over the test duration, reflecting a slight widening of the particle size distribution. This comprehensive analysis confirms that attrition not only reduces the average particle size but also alters the overall distribution characteristics, with preferential generation of fine particles.

3.2.3. Particle attrition in mechanical conveyors

The same batch of olivine particles (initial $d_{50} \sim 75$ μm) was used in both pneumatic and mechanical conveying tests to allow for a direct comparison of attrition severity under different conditions.

Results from the impeller tumbler tests indicated even lower attrition rates compared to pneumatic conveying. Results are illustrated in Supplementary Information. Metal specimens are mounted onto a rotating shaft and continuously rotated through a bed of olivine placed inside a trough. This setup allowed for the operation at the low-speed dense granular flow conditions expected in the storage tanks during discharge, in the screw conveyors, and through the heat exchangers. The system design also ensured a near-zero angle of contact between the particles and the screw conveyor trough. With the moderate rotation speeds, any wear from particle impact is near negligible, and pure abrasion wear is not observed.

Experiments demonstrated that the operating temperature does not affect the particle attrition. After 1000 h, particle sizes were reduced from 75 μm to 70.5 μm . These size reductions are negligible in view of the operation time. The obvious reason is the creation of a stagnant particle layer near the auger bottom. The level of attrition in the P2P mechanical conveyors can hence be considered as negligible.

3.3. Erosion and material selection

3.3.1. Erosion rates

A surface will be attacked by the impact of conveyed particles. This type of wear is generally described as erosion. Erosion is a continuing problem in such units as pneumatic conveying. Despite being an undesirable phenomenon, erosion is successfully applied in, e.g., sand

Fig. 10. Selection of piping and vessel construction materials.

blasting and the erosive drilling of hard materials.

Previous research by P2P team members established that erosion is only detrimental to construction materials in fluidized beds if the particle velocities exceed about 30 m/s [8,28]. In the P2P application, velocities will be below 0.2 m/s, and erosion is therefore considered less of a problem. The velocity of 0.2 m/s refers to the very low relative velocities in the screw conveyor and hoppers, where a protective particle layer forms. This is distinct from the higher velocities in the pneumatic riser.

In the mechanical transport equipment (screw conveying) no erosion was measured, due to the protective particle layer formed near the conveyor's auger (mixing blades end at about 1 mm from the auger's wall).

The situation is different in the pneumatic loop. Since the construction material contains ~25 wt % of Cr, the evolution of erosion can be determined from the measured Cr concentration in the particle flow. Samples of the olivine were collected at different time intervals, Cr was leached by nitric acid, and the resulting solution was submitted to ICP-MS measurement. The most relevant results are illustrated in Fig. 9 below, at the expected P2P operating conditions.

The Cr concentration is expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ olivine in circulation. The erosion rate is limited to 0.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ after 1000 h. with 106 m^3/h (138 kg/h) of air and a solid rate of respectively 606 ($S/A = 4.4$) or 2811 kg/h ($S/A = 20.4$), the amount of metal wear is a maximum of 1.68 mg/h. Considering a total weight of the experimental steel construction at about 90 kg, or 22.5 kg Cr, the hourly erosion rate is 0.0075 %.

Although particles have a lower slip velocity in dense-phase conveying ($S/A = 20.4$) than in lean-phase conveying ($S/A = 4.4$), the higher mass concentration of particles in the conveying air increases the wear rate.

Experiments at different S/A ratios should elucidate this phenomenon, but they were impossible within the timeframe of the present research, and the long-duration (1000 h) of each experimental run.

Given the low gravitational fall velocity and the formation of a core-annulus flow with a slow-moving particle layer at the wall, erosion in the downcomer is expected to be negligible and significantly lower than in the pneumatic riser. This is a very acceptable erosion rate, even in the operational case of 16 000 kg/h of solids circulating through the pipe and associated auxiliaries. It is however recommended to specifically address the construction of the bends, preferably in an inverted L shape, to accumulate a static layer of solids, and having "low" bends (radius of curvature equal to 6 x pipe diameter) to avoid high velocity impact on the – otherwise – 90° angled bends.

3.3.2. Selection of construction materials

3.3.2.1. Preliminary considerations. For CSP applications, the construction materials must operate at high temperature and withstand the thermal cycling between varying process conditions, i.e., from a cold start-up to high temperature operation. The expected corrosion in an oxidizing (air) atmosphere is an additional key issue. A few relevant criteria were used for a preliminary assessment, as presented in Fig. 10.

Although particles have a lower slip velocity in dense-phase conveying ($S/A = 20.4$) than in lean-phase conveying ($S/A = 4.4$), the higher mass concentration of particles in the conveying air increases the wear rate.

This is an important finding, emphasizing that excessively high S/A values in dense-phase conveying can counteract the reduced particle velocity. Experiments at different S/A ratios should elucidate this phenomenon, but they were impossible within the timeframe of the present research, and the long-duration (1000 h) of each experimental run.

Thermo-mechanical properties need to be considered and will determine the required geometry (pressures to deformation and rupture, wall thickness). ASTM A240, ASTM A555, and testing standards ASTM E139 are important in this respect. These steel and alloy properties are available in handbooks or in technical leaflets of suppliers. Few data are available for ceramic materials and other alloys such as Hastelloy, FeCr-alloy, and Iron Aluminide. Their applications in the solar P2P plant are indicative of cost and unnecessary better behaviour when exposed to the temperatures under scrutiny. It is, however, clear that AISI 310 has a fair to excellent behaviour in high temperature and oxidizing environments. It is, moreover, 2 to 3 times cheaper than Incoloy and more readily available on the market of steel suppliers.

3.3.2.2. Experimental assessment. The P2P research investigated these thermo-mechanical properties.

(1) Mechanical properties after thermal cycling

Six identical samples of AISI 310 tubes (39 mm O.D., 2 mm wall thickness), with one sample not being subjected to the T-cycling (used as a blank), were investigated for thermal cycling. Five pipes were subjected to up to 1000 cycles of heating to 800 °C in an electric furnace, and subsequent air cooling at 200 °C. Pressure resistance testing was performed in a pull/press testing unit of Feiyao Hydraulic. Deformation was observed at 14.8 MPa for the blank tube, but reduced to 14.1 MPa after 1000 heating cycles. Under the same conditions, the pressure to burst achieved 41.6 to 39.4 MPa, respectively. Both experimental critical pressures correspond with calculated values by the Barlow equation

Fig. 11. Comparison of the oxide thickness. When no bars are shown, measurements are below measurement accuracy.

[29].

The calculated wall thickness required at as high a pressure as 5 bar and 800 °C was < 0.03 mm, far below current commercial pipe thicknesses. In the P2P operations, high pressures are not encountered (maximum 1.3 bar in the receiver and upflow riser). Other equipment will be subjected to a maximum pressure load of 100 mbar. Wall thicknesses of 2 mm are hence certainly sufficient to guarantee a long cycle life.

(2) Corrosion testing

Corrosion testing enables to selection of the most appropriate materials to manufacture the various process units. Various steel grades needed to be tested at high temperature (AISI 316 L, AISI 310, Inconel 601 and 625, and Incoloy 800 HT). Specimens were exposed for 1000 h in an atmospheric (air) environment, at conditions of ambient humidity. At the end of the test, N₂ was applied to flush the test gas and cool the furnace.

For **Weight change testing**, the furnace specimen holders were cooled and placed into a desiccator before weighing. After visual inspection, the specimens were weighed to assess the rate of loss of corrosion product during the tests. For numerous specimens (e.g., AISI 316 L), the corrosion product layer had spalled, representing a weight loss. The weight gain due to the formed oxide layer is limited for most of the materials tested and measured between 3 and 20 mg/cm² for e.g., Inconel 690 and AISI 310. After weighing the complete specimen, the oxidation protection layers were purposely removed, with a weight loss between 5 and 32 mg/cm² as a result.

For **Corrosion testing**, sectioned specimens were embedded in a thin layer of Epofix resin to prevent damaging the corrosion product layers during cutting. The sections were then polished to 1 µm and viewed by an optical microscope to measure the thickness of the oxide layers. Results are summarized in Fig. 11.

Optical microscope imaging revealed that the damage rate during 1000 h experiments can be compared as µm/hr of damaged alloy surface. Hastelloy X had a maximum damage rate in air at ~0.1 µm/hr. The damage rate of other alloys was between 0.001 and 0.05 µm/hr. These values are low in oxidizing conditions, and on average, below 0.015 µm/hr. The life span of a 2 mm thick pipe will exceed 66,000 h (~16 years at 4000 h/year).

The measured damage rates (0.001–0.05 µm/h) imply that a pipe wall with a thickness of 2 mm would be consumed in 40,000 to 2000,000 h. Taking a conservative average damage rate of 0.015 µm/h, the lifespan of a 2 mm thick pipe is estimated to exceed 66,000 h (~16.5

Table 5
Fundamental properties.

Property	Values and comments	Impact
Particle attrition in the pneumatic conveying loop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A small amount of particle attrition was measured; higher at a high solid/air ratio than at a low ratio - Temperature has no significant effect - The attrition rate is <0.08 wt % of the particle conveying rate at high solid/air conveying ratios 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Velocity in the lifter (vertical conveying loop) should preferably be limited to 15 m/s - limited effect of temperature - for the P2P application, with a solids circulation rate of a maximum 16 ton/h, the creation of fines will be about 272 kg/h. These fines need to be collected in the gas-solid separation unit.
Particle attrition in mechanical conveyors (µm)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At rotational speeds of 10 to 25 rpm, the particle attrition lowered the particle size by <6 % after 1000 h. -Temperature effects are negligible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no effect of operating temperature - provide a stagnant particle layer between the scroll (impellers) and the auger walls.
Particle agglomeration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No increase in d₉₀ was measured - No agglomeration occurred 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - not of specific concern
Particle-driven erosion in pneumatic conveying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Erosion rate of construction material is < 0.0075 % 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Special attention is needed for high velocity particle impacts in the bends by either using bends of high radius of curvature, or constructing the bends in an inverted L-shape - not of specific concern.
Particle-driven erosion in mechanical conveying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No erosion of construction materials was measured, due to the static particle layer underneath the scroll (impeller) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - not of specific concern.
Dust emission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited to the amount of fines in the feed olivine, and to the amount of fines formed in the conveying loop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fines of the feed olivine will be collected at start-up - operational fines (max. 1278 kg/h will need to be continuously collected
Emission abatement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From the various solid-gas separation techniques, the cyclone offers the advantages of simplicity and maturity - Measurements using a High-efficiency Stairmand cyclone reveal a capture efficiency at high temperature in excess of 96 % for 1.5 µm dust - The high particle density of olivine counteracts the expected efficiency loss due to the higher operating temperature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The use of a Stairmand or Van Tongeren High-efficiency cyclone operating at 3.6 m/s is recommended. - the cyclone pressure drop will be <15.3 mbar (against 20 mbar at 4 m/s)
Construction materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AISI 310 offers excellent properties and has a high resistance to deformation and bursting. - It is moreover a lot cheaper and more widely available on the steel markets/ - The oxide layer formed protects the underlying steel matrix from oxidative corrosion - the damage rate is between 0.001 and 0.05 µm/ht 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Construction of all equipment should be performed in AISI 310. Only for parts at 900 °C (e.g., receiver tubes) could Incoloy 600 be a better solution. - The damage rate is low, and a 2 mm thick pipe will have a life duration of about 16 years. A 3 mm thick pipe will be operational for at least 24 years.

years at 4000 operational hours/year). This extrapolation from 1000-hour laboratory tests to years of operational service assumes a linear erosion rate and does not account for potential unforeseen operational transients, start-up/shutdown cycles, or other long-term degradation mechanisms. While the results are highly promising, these projections should be treated as a best-case scenario, and continuous monitoring in a real-world installation will be essential to validate these lifespan estimates. A 3 mm thick wall would correspondingly extend the lifespan to approximately 24 years.

3.4. Summary of findings and scale-up considerations

The results of different investigations with respect to the particle attrition and particle-driven erosion behaviour as a function of the temperature lead to a selection of possible construction materials. These results determine the design and operation of the P2P concept. The impact is summarized in the following Table 5.

4. Conclusions

This study has presented a comprehensive experimental and analytical investigation into the design and operation of a particle conveyance loop for a next-generation CSP system. Using the fundamental and practical findings of the research present final design and operation recommendations for the P2P pilot plant, and toward a future scale-up were presented. The detailed engineering design established key parameters for the riser and downcomer, ensuring stable operation with a specific energy consumption of only 0.35 kW/ton. Material selection, based on a comprehensive evaluation of thermo-mechanical properties and cost, confirmed the suitability of AISI 410 and 310 steels for long-term operation in their respective temperature regimes.

From the experimental assessment of the erosion rate of the metal constructions presented in this study, it was determined that the erosion damage will be limited and will guarantee an equipment lifespan of 16 to 24 years. The 16–24 year lifespan is based on the experimentally determined wear rates of 0.015 $\mu\text{m}/\text{h}$. For a 2 mm thick pipe and 4000 h/year of operation (on-sun periods), half the pipe wall thickness will be eroded in about 16 years (66,000 h). A 3 mm thick wall, as used in the downcomer, will see its lifespan extended to approximately 24 years. Attrition of particles will be limited in the screw conveyors, in the dense-phase riser, and the stick-slip flow down-comer.

Thermal modeling confirmed that overall heat losses can be maintained below 3 % via optimized heat recovery from the conveying air. Also, operating at higher solid/air mass flow ratios will significantly reduce the air-driven losses. It is finally concluded that all unit operations of the present particle conveying loop can be applied on a large scale, although some geometric modifications might be required.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Yimin Deng: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Data curation. **Alex Le Gal:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology. **Emmanuel Guillot:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Investigation. **Gilles Flamant:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Jan Baeyens:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.rineng.2025.108532](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.108532).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- [1] G. Flamant, B. Grange, J. Wheeldon, F. Siros, B. Valentin, F. Bataille, H. Zhang, Y. Deng, J. Baeyens, Opportunities and challenges in using particle circulation loops for concentrated solar power applications, *Prog. Energy Combust. Sci.* 94 (2023) 101056, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pecs.2022.101056>.
- [2] Next-CSP project website, (n.d.). <http://next-csp.eu/>.
- [3] Q. Kang, G. Flamant, R. Dewil, J. Baeyens, H.L. Zhang, Y.M. Deng, Particles in a circulation loop for solar energy capture and storage, *Particuology* 43 (2019) 149–156, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2018.01.009>.
- [4] J. Baeyens, D. van Gauwbergen, I. Vinckier, Pneumatic drying: the use of large-scale experimental data in a design procedure, *Powder Technol.* 83 (1995) 139–148, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910\(94\)02945-K](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910(94)02945-K).
- [5] P. Guo, Q.H. Ly, W.L. Saw, K.-S. Lim, P.J. Ashman, G.J. Nathan, A technical assessment of pneumatic conveying of solids for a high temperature particle receiver, in: 2019: p. 030025. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5117537>.
- [6] S. Alaqel, N.S. Saleh, R.S. Saeed, E. Djajadiwinata, A. Alswaiyd, M. Sarfraz, H. Al-Ansary, A. El-Leathy, Z. Al-Suhaibani, S. Danish, S. Jeter, Z. Almutairi, An experimental demonstration of the effective application of thermal energy storage in a particle-based CSP system, *Sustainability* 14 (2022) 5316, <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14095316>.
- [7] M. Sarfraz, R. Yeung, K. Repole, M. Golob, S. Jeter, H. Al-Ansary, A. El-Leathy, S. Alaqel, N.S. Saleh, R. Saeed, A. Alswaiyd, Proposed design and integration of 1.3 MWe pre-commercial demonstration particle heating receiver based concentrating Solar power plant, in: ASME 2021 15th International Conference on Energy Sustainability, American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.1115/ES2021-62529>.
- [8] S.-Y. Wu, J. Baeyens, C.-Y. Chu, Effect of the grid-velocity on attrition in gas fluidized beds, *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* 77 (1999) 738–744, <https://doi.org/10.1002/cjce.5450770415>.
- [9] H. Zhang, H. Benoit, D. Gauthier, J. Degève, J. Baeyens, I.P. López, M. Hemati, G. Flamant, Particle circulation loops in solar energy capture and storage: gas–solid flow and heat transfer considerations, *Appl. Energy* 161 (2016) 206–224, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2015.10.005>.
- [10] K. Kant, R. Pitchumani, Erosion wear analysis of heat exchange surfaces in a falling particle-based concentrating solar power system, *Sol. Energy Mater. Sol. Cells* 266 (2024) 112629, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2023.112629>.
- [11] P. Domínguez-Coy, J.I. Córcoles, J.A. Almendros-Ibáñez, Review on erosion of horizontal tubes immersed in fluidized beds of Geldart B particles, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 196 (2024) 114359, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2024.114359>.
- [12] S. Li, J. Baeyens, R. Dewil, L. Appels, H. Zhang, Y. Deng, Advances in rigid porous high temperature filters, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 139 (2021) 110713, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.110713>.
- [13] X. Zheng, S. Yin, Y. Ding, L. Wang, Experimental study on high concentration entrainment of ultrafine powder, *Powder Technol.* 344 (2019) 133–139, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2018.12.025>.
- [14] J.M. Wheeldon, J. Baeyens, S. Li, Y. Deng, A new design approach for the established flow region of vertical, dilute-phase pneumatic conveyors, *Particuology* 66 (2022) 10–20, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2021.06.013>.
- [15] D. Geldart, *Gas Fluidization Technology*, John Wiley, Chichester (UK), 1986.
- [16] David Mills, Part D.: Conveying system design, in: Butterworths (Ed.), *Pneumatic Conveying Design Guide*, 3rd edition, London, 1990.
- [17] Y. Deng, F. Sabatier, R. Dewil, G. Flamant, A. Le Gal, R. Gueguen, J. Baeyens, S. Li, R. Ansart, Dense upflow fluidized bed (DUFFB) solar receivers of high aspect ratio: different fluidization modes through inserting bubble rupture promoters, *Chem. Eng. J.* 418 (2021) 129376, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.129376>.
- [18] F. Rizk, A comparison between horizontal and vertical pneumatic conveying systems considering the optimal operating conditions, *J. Powder Bulk J. Powder Bulk Solids Technol.* 7 (1983) 5–11. <https://pascal-francis.inist.fr/vibad/index.php?action=getRecordDetail&idt=9652452>.
- [19] D.V. Punwani, M.V. Modi, P.B. Tarman, Generalized correlation for estimating choking velocity in vertical solids transport, in: *International Powder and Bulk*

- Solids Handling and Processing Conference, Institute of Gas Technology, 1976. Chicago, IL, USA, <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/7230596>.
- [20] H. Zhang, W. Kong, T. Tan, F. Gilles, J. Baeyens, Experiments support an improved model for particle transport in fluidized beds, *Sci. Rep.* 7 (2017) 10178, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-10597-3>.
- [21] D. Geldart, Types of gas fluidization, *Powder Technol.* 7 (1973) 285–292, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910\(73\)80037-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/0032-5910(73)80037-3).
- [22] C.W. Chan, J. Seville, X. Fan, J. Baeyens, Solid particle motion in a standpipe as observed by Positron emission particle tracking, *Powder Technol.* 194 (2009) 58–66, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2009.03.032>.
- [23] AZO materials, The state of scientific marketing. <https://www.azom.com/search.aspx?q=properties&site=all&fsb=1>, 2025 accessed August 28, 2025.
- [24] N. Goel, T. Mei-Lin Fong, J.P. Shingledecker, A. Russell, M.W. Keller, S.A. Shirazi, T. Otanicar, Effect of temperature on abrasion erosion in particle based concentrating solar powerplants, *Sol. Energy* 224 (2021) 1127–1135, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2021.06.080>.
- [25] R. Dewil, J. Baeyens, B. Caerts, CFB cyclones at high temperature: operational results and design assessment, *Particuology* 6 (2008) 149–156, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2008.01.002>.
- [26] B.A. Kozur, R.J. Berry, S. Zigan, P. García-Triñanes, M.S.A. Bradley, Particle attrition mechanisms, their characterisation, and application to horizontal lean phase pneumatic conveying systems: a review, *Powder Technol.* 334 (2018) 76–105, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2018.04.047>.
- [27] H. Zhang, J. Degrève, J. Baeyens, S.Y. Wu, Powder attrition in gas fluidized beds, *Powder Technol.* (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2015.08.052>.
- [28] Q. Kang, R. Dewil, J. Degrève, J. Baeyens, H. Zhang, Energy analysis of a particle suspension solar combined cycle power plant, *Energy Convers. Manag.* (2018), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2018.02.067>.
- [29] V.Mark. Durand, D.H. Barlow, *Essentials of Abnormal Psychology*, 7th ed., Cengage Learning, Mason, OH, 2016.